

THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIONS

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Abstract: In the article, scientific, technical and innovation potential is one of the key factors in the country's socio-economic development. In particular, the role of the state scientific, technical and innovation policy in the economy in solving the socio-economic problems that arose in the course of reforms was emphasized.

Keywords: innovation potential, science and technology, efficiency, scientific and technical potential.

Introduction

The rational and high-level use of scientific, technical and innovative resources is one of the important and urgent tasks in the development of advanced sectors of the economy, increasing the scientific potential of Gross domestic product, and the widespread development of products with high added value. The scientific and technical potential of the country and the level of use of innovative resources are characterized by a number of indicators. These include the cost of research and development, the dynamics of the volume of work and services performed by research institutions and organizations, the share of research and development in Gross domestic product, the change in the number of research organizations, institutes and centers and their number, the network structure of scientific and technical potential, import and export of inventions and new developments in the form of patents and licenses, etc.

The scientific, technical and innovative potential of the country serves a common goal - to ensure the development of science and technology. However, individually, each of them performs its functions and has a different effect on socio-economic development. Scientific potential is the sum of conditions and resources for fundamental scientific research. Scientific and technical potential is a set of conditions and resources for the implementation of applied R&D, in particular, experimental design and experimental technological work. Innovation potential is a set of conditions and resources that serve to ensure the application of research and development in practice, including production. In this regard, scientific, technical and innovation potential are interdependent and interdependent and are separate parts of the scientific and innovation process.

Literature review

The Republic of Korea pursues a policy of development of 5 directions of scientific and technical research:

The primary focus was on areas where economic benefits could be quickly reaped. Examples are computer science, chemical engineering, and mechanical engineering.

The second area includes biotechnology and the development of new materials, which can be expected in the medium term.

The third area deals with issues related to science and the environment, health and well-being of the population, which play an important role for society as a whole.

The fourth area is oceanography and aeronautics with medium to long term results.

The fifth direction is the development of all areas of science and technology, regardless of the period of obtaining economic benefits.

Currently, the economy of the Republic of Korea combines knowledge-intensive industries with labor-intensive and capital-intensive ones. The search for new options for harmonizing the market and a plan for modernizing the state structural policy has become relevant. The content of this policy cannot be determined by listing its parts. Undoubtedly, investment programs, price regulation, various measures to balance foreign trade turnover, credit policy, market contingent, tax, anti-inflationary policy are components of the structural policy. The main goal of the structural policy is to create an integral, modern self-sustaining growth economy, to create a mechanism for market planning of economic development.

Data and methods

The birth of new, advanced ideas, fundamental research, applied research, experimental design and experimental technological development, experimental design, industrial testing, production mastering, serial production, commercial goals, new. The process of widespread use of the product in practice consists of interrelated stages of a single scientific and technical development.

In the creation and development of the scientific and technical base for development, three important areas can be distinguished:

1. Creation of news in general;
2. Development of fundamental and practical knowledge, which is the "basic" technology in the implementation of innovations, development of production;
3. Creation of technological infrastructure, that is research and development, engineering and technical support of production. Important elements of the technological infrastructure are standards, metrology, quality control, measurement methods and much more.

Results

Today, the relationship between science and technology is evolving at an unprecedented pace. Production, as in the previous period, is developing not by one person, but on the basis of research carried out by scientific communities. Research aimed at the further development of technology and technology, the search for technical solutions based on new principles, began to be fully financed from material resources and funding. There are many opportunities for future research. The integration of science and industry has become an integral part of current market relations and innovation processes, and thanks to it, science increasingly demonstrates that it is a decisive force in production. In developed countries, this integration is reflected in various forms of cooperation between fundamental academic science (research carried out in universities, their laboratories and research centers, institutes of the Academy of Sciences) and research in practice-oriented enterprises and firms. The call for cooperation between the two sides is the development of science and technology.

In the development of any technique and technology, three main stages can be distinguished:

- 1) the period of concealment in the formation of the basic principle and "critical mass" of material and technical means;
- 2) a period of intensive development;
- 3) the period when there is a slowdown in growth rates when approaching the limiting indicators of physical and technological development.

For example, in microelectronics, the degree of integration has increased, that is, the number of transistors in one integrated circuit.

Conclusion

I would like to briefly outline a number of key areas of activity and measures for the formation and further development of an innovative economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- To study all technological knowledge and innovations that we need in developed countries, and gradually apply them in the branches of the republic's economy in the national interests;
- Attracting investors and foreign capital to key domestic innovation projects;
- Creation of a knowledge base on technological innovations and its availability for all citizens through the Internet portal;
- Development of innovations, ensuring reliable protection of intellectual property while transforming achievements in this area into products with high added value.

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